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Optimization of Bacteriocin Producing Probiotic *Lactobacillus* Spp. Isolated From Broiler Chicken Gut

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Abstract

Thirteen presumptive thermo-tolerant *Lactobacilli* isolates were isolated from the small intestines of domestic chickens (*Gallus domessticus*) and were tested against various commercial antibiotics used in chicken feed to test antibiotic resistance of *Lactobacillus* spp. Isolates were identified by generating dendrogram based on biochemical profiling results which was confirmed using PCR reaction. Bacteriocin produced by *Lactobacillus* sp. was optimized at different physicochemical factors which showed satisfactory zone of inhibition against pathogenic test organisms, both with and without purification. Four out of thirteen confirmed *Lactobacillus* sp. isolates showed resistance against Ciprofloxacin and one isolate showed resistance against erythromycin. A dendrogram was generated using biotyping where the isolates exhibited similarity to different species situated at same clusters and PCR assay confirmed isolates as *Lactobacillus* sp. upto genus level. *Lactobacillus* population will not decrease even after consumption of Erythromycin and Ciprofloxacin by humans to control gastroenteritis caused by enterobacteriace and probiotic activity of *Lactobacillus* sp. will not decrease and interfered by resistant antibiotics. Bacteriocin showed active bactericidal activity against *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *S. typhi*, *B. subtilis*, *B. megaterium*, *B. cereus*, *K. pneumoniae* and *E. fecalis*. Future prospect involves purification of bacteriocin, MIC and MBC of produced Bacteriocin against test isolates.

Key words: Probiotic, *Lactobacillus* spp. Bacteriocin, Bioactive.

Introduction

The natural intestinal floras are a protective barrier against pathogens that can also affect nutrient digestion and absorption. Probiotics refer to live microbial food supplements that benefit the host by improving intestinal microbial balance [1]. Commercial probiotics consist of either one or more strains of bacteria, among which, lactic acid bacteria (LAB) are deemed significant [15]. In vivo studies conducted for the effect of *Lactobacillus* sp. are time-consuming and often expensive; thus in vitro tests reduce work load and find the most effective organism. Antibacterial and colonization activity are characteristics for selection of LAB as probiotic as they provide reduced colonization of enteric pathogens by competitiveness [15]. Recent studies have been conducted to increase

probiotic efficacy and role as supplements in poultry nutrition [15]. The beneficial effects include the production of α -amylase, phytase, β -glucanase, xylanase, and cellulase enzymes by *Lactobacillus* [8] show the importance of bacteriocin producing bacterial strains selected for chicken probiotics which can improve digestion [15]- [8] *Lactobacillus* is a genus of non-spore-forming Gram positive bacilli which belong to a lactic acid bacteria group [12]. *Lactobacillus* protects the host against pathogens, and intake nutrients from the host, thus forming a mutualism [13]. *Lactobacillus* is the most common probiotic present in food and capable of maintaining human well-being by helping in the treatment of gastrointestinal, vaginal infections, and skin disorders by its various applications [10]. Many *Lactobacillus* species are used as starter cultures for ferment-

tation in the production of various fermented foods, animal feeds and soil amendment. The antimicrobial activity of *Lactobacillus* species relies on bacteriocin and low molecular weight compounds' production that inhibits growth of microbes [10]-[9]. Bacteriocins are products derived from bacteria which are pretentious or peptide toxins in nature, capable of inhibiting the growth bacterial strain(s). Possessing similar killing factor in yeast and paramecium killing factors, and also structurally, functionally, and ecologically diverse while being tested to assess applications as narrow-spectrum antibiotics [5]. In recent years, multi-drug resistant pathogens are emerging which is responsible for inflicting public health, environmental and economic damage to developing countries similar to Bangladesh to combat which a suitable approach is becoming necessary. The probiotic is a live microbial feed supplement which positively affects the health of the host animal by improving its intestinal balance. In recent years, research related to bacteriocins is garnering attention rise in antibiotic resistance among pathogenic bacteria and the presence of pathogenic microbes present in the food [4]-[3]. This research was conducted in order to optimize production in different physicochemical conditions in order to determine the yield of bacteriocin production by *Lactobacillus* spp

Methods and Materials

Sample Collection and Processing

LAB strains were isolated from contents of the crop, proventriculus, gizzard, ileum and ceca of adult chicken. The sample was mixed and homogenized with sterile saline buffer (0.85%, pH 7.0). Decimal dilution of these samples were mixed with MRS broth (Difco) and incubated at 45°C for 48 h under anaerobic conditions [7]

Isolation and Identification of Isolates

Samples were serially diluted and inoculated upon Nutrient agar and MRS agar media plates by spread inoculation. After inoculation media were incubated for 24 hours at 37°C. Post incubation colonies were randomly selected from each MRS agar plate.

Biotyping of LAB Strains

The pure cultures were characterized based on similarity of LAB strains at identax database [6]. Data were uploaded as Binary data were positive results were denoted as 1 and negative results as 0. Uploaded data were compared with standard characteristics of *Lactobacillus* spp. present in identax database. Similarity between isolates with *Lactobacillus* strains were determined by using complete linkage, under multivariate cluster analysis using STATA 14 software [11]-[2].

Determination of Probiotic Efficiency

pH tolerance and temperature sensitivity one set of Isolates were inoculated into the sterile MRS broth of varying pH, i.e., 4.5, 5, 6, 7 and 8 and incubated at 37 °C for 24-48 h, while another set of inoculated MRS broth was grown at varying temperatures, i.e., 15, 30, 37, 45 and 60 °C for 24-48 h. The absorbance of MRS broths was taken at 600 nm by a spectrophotometer to measure microbial load [14]. NaCl tolerance MRS broth made with increasing concentrations of NaCl (1, 3, 5 and 10%) were inoculated with each *Lactobacillus* isolates and incubated at 37 °C for overnight. Then the observance of MRS broths was taken at 600 nm by a spectrophotometer for measuring microbial load [14].

Antibiotic susceptibility test the antibiotic susceptibility of *Lactobacillus* was assessed by using Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method on MRS agar plates. The used antibiotics were penicillin g (10 IU), chloramphenicol (30 µg), erythromycin (15 µg), cefixime (5 µg), cephadrine (30 µg), streptomycin (10 µg) and rifamycin (5 µg) [2].

Determination of Crude and Purified Bacteriocin Production Capability of the *L. Plantarum* MG1 and *L. Delbrueckii* MT4

One milliliter of frozen *Lactobacillus* isolate was cultured 24 h in 20 mL MRS broth. Then 1 mL culture was subcultured 24 h in 20 mL MRS

broth. Cells were removed by centrifuging at 9000 rpm for 15 min. 100 µL of the pH unadjusted aliquot of cell free supernatant (CFS) was added to the first well [14]. The remaining CFS was adjusted to pH 6.0 with 1M NH₄OH (1M/1N NaOH) in order to rule out possible inhibitory effects due to organic acids. One hundred micro liter of the pH adjusted CFS was filtered and added to the second well. Both the control and samples were assayed for antimicrobial activity by using agar well diffusion method [2]-[14].

Strain Identification

The strain LTI16 was examined by the gram stain and catalase tests and then identified by a PCR-based method. Total DNA was extracted using a DNA extraction method. Briefly, the bacterial cells were added to extraction solution. The Sample was phenol-chloroform extracted and the DNA was precipitated using an equal volume of isopropanol. The DNA was washed by using 70% ethanol. The semi-dried extract DNA was stored at -20°C until use. Identification was carried out based on primers targeted against variable regions of the 16S rRNA genes. The universal primer pair consisted of the forward (5' GAG AGT TTG ATC CTG GCT CAG 3') and reverse (5' GAA AGG AGG TGA TCC AGC CG 3'), which were used for amplification of 16S rRNA. Deoxyribonucleic acid amplification of the (~1,500 bases) fragment was carried out in a 50-µL reaction mixture containing 5 µL of 10 × PCR buffer, 1 µL deoxynucleoside triphosphate mixture (10 mM), 1.4 µL of MgCl₂ (50 mM), 2 µL of each primer (10 pmol µL⁻¹), 2 µL of DNA (10ng), and 0.4 µL of Taq DNA polymerase (5 U µL⁻¹). Amplification was performed in a thermo cycler using the following program. A 5-min denaturation period at 95°C was followed by 30 cycles each: 1 min at 95°C, 1 min at 53°C, and 1 min at 72°C. Then DNA was analyzed.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis of ZOI obtained from both unpurified and purified bacteriocin was conducted in form of Analysis of Variance, single factor in Microsoft excel.

Antibiogram Test

Antibiotic sensitivity of the strain was determined by the Kirby-Bauer disc method except that MRS agar was used instead of Mueller-Hinton culture medium. The density of bacterial suspension was adjusted until the visible turbidity was equal to 0.5 McFarland standards. The inoculum was spread evenly over the entire surface of the plates. Subsequently, paper discs containing the antibiotics were laid on the plates and incubated an aerobically at 37°C and growth inhibition was examined after 24 h [2].

Result and Discussion

Determination of Probiotic Efficiency

Figure 1. Effect of pH Tolerance, Temperature Sensitivity and NaCl Tolerance

Bio-typing of *Lactobacillus* isolates

Dendrogram generated based on similarity between *Lactobacillus* isolates revealed Isolate I1 and I3 have complete similarity with *Lactobacillus casei*, where I2 posses similarity with *Lactobacillus acidophilus*. I4 on the other hand exhibited 95% biotype similarity with *Lactobacillus acidophilus*.

Table 1. Antimicrobial Activity of Isolates against Pathogen

Organism	E. coli	E. fecalis	B. subtilis	B. cereus	B. megaterium	S. typhi	S. aureus	S. pneumoniae
I-1	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
I-2	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
I-3	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
I-4	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
I-5	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+
I-6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
I-7	-	-	+	-	+	-	-	-
I-8	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
I-9	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
I-10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Figure 2. Dendrogram of Lactobacillus Isolates Based on Carbohydrate profiling

Antimicrobial Activity

Table 1, Figure 3

Figure 3. Zone of Inhibition Produced by Lactobacillus Isolates without and After Purification

Antibiotic Susceptibility Test

Figure 4

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis conducted in Microsoft excels revealed data from both unpurified and purified bacteriocin with a P value of 0.021 and 0.029 respectively. Which is statistically significant (p<0.05). The P value of antibiogram conducted for Lactobacillus isolates also revealed to be statistically significant (P value= 0.025, P<0.05) The goal of this research work was to isolate potential probiotic bacteria. Based on the biotype characteristics four [12] isolates were selected as probiotics from chicken gut samples. The isolates pos-

Figure 4. Antibiogram of Lactobacillus spp. against Commercial antibiotics C=Chloramphenicol, Cip= Ciprofloxacin, E= Erythromycin, Te= Tetracycline.

sess most of the characteristics of Lactobacillus spp. The significant growth of isolates on MRS–agar plates in anaerobic conditions confirmed that the isolates were Lactobacillus spp. The phenotypic and biochemical characters, compared with the data of identax [6], allowing identification of the four isolates. Adequate numbers of viable cells of probiotic viable strains should reach the intestinal tract. In order to survive the passage through the gastrointestinal tract, resistance to low pH, bile salt and proteolytic enzymes is needed. The phenotypic and biochemical characters, compared with the data of Carr et al., allowing identifying the four isolates. 4 out of 10 confirmed Lactobacillus sp. isolates showed resistance against Ciprofloxacin and one isolate showed resistance against erythromycin.

The isolates were tested against various commercial antibiotics used in chicken feed to test antibiotic resistance of Lactobacillus spp. 3 out of 4 isolates showed resistance against Ciprofloxacin and one isolate showed resistance against erythromycin. Resistance of Lactobacillus against these antibiotics is a positive prospect as lactobacillus population will not decrease even after consumption of erythromycin and ciprofloxacin by humans to control gastroenteritis caused by enterobacteriaceae. The Probiotic activity of Lactobacillus will not decrease and interfered by resistant antibiotics. However, this could become a threat as a resistance mechanism could be plasmid mediated and can be conjugated to potential pathogens. Though the possibility of this is narrow, but the chance still remains. Bacteriocin showed active bactericidal activity against E. coli, S. aureus, S. typhi, B. Subtillis, B. megaterium, B. cereus, K. pneumoniae and E. fecalis. The studies proved helpful in the isolation and identification of a Lactobacillus strain which can be used as a potent culture for probiotic manufacturing. The strain can also be used for protease production, which can then be used for coagulating milk casein in the cheese manufacturing as the strain has a high caseinolytic activity. SDS PAGE assay can confirm the type of Bacteriocin produced while species specific PCR assay can be used for confirmation of Lactobacillus isolates based on the results

from biotyping. Future aspects around research with *Lactobacillus* spp. involves Optimization of bacteriocin production, purification of bacteriocin, SDS-PAGE assay for bacteriocin protein profile, PCR assay for species confirmation, and antibiotic activity of bacteriocin produced by *Lactobacillus* sp.

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